

POLYMER HYDROGEL – APPLICATION RATE AND WATER SAVINGS

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Annotation

This article presents the results of field experiments conducted on meadow sierozem soils in the Tashkent region, where 40 kg per hectare of polymer hydrogel was applied for the joint cultivation of cotton and soybean. The results demonstrate that during the growing season, the efficiency of irrigation water use increased by 15–17%, and it became possible to achieve a cotton yield of 30.7 centners per hectare.

Introduction: Preserving and consistently improving the productivity and meliorative state of our valuable irrigated lands, as well as ensuring the efficient use of irrigation water, are currently stimulating further research by our scientists and sector specialists.

Ensuring adequate water supply for agricultural crops, saving irrigation water, and obtaining two or more harvests from the same field within a single season through the use of innovative technologies have become crucial.

In this regard, various scientific studies have been carried out by researchers, including cultivating two different crops simultaneously on a single plot, achieving high and quality yields, maintaining and enhancing soil fertility, stabilizing the meliorative condition of irrigated lands, producing additional food products, and using hydrogels in crop production to reduce water consumption. These scientific efforts aim to increase the efficiency of land and water use in cotton farming, support the economic stability of farming enterprises, and open new opportunities for farmers during market reform periods.

Research Methods: To address the aforementioned issues, for the first time we conducted field studies in the conditions of medium and heavy loamy meadow sierozem soils at the “Mamatkarim Dilshodjon” farm located in the Orta Chirchik district of Tashkent region. In these studies, polymer hydrogel was applied for the joint cultivation of leguminous crops (soybean) with cotton. The objective was to explore the influence of this method on soil fertility, seasonal

water use, cotton productivity, and the overall efficiency of land and water resource utilization. These efforts were directed toward providing scientific solutions for increasing food supply, preventing ecological and meliorative degradation of the environment, expanding agricultural production, and improving the economic efficiency of farming.

The significance of hydrogel use in agriculture, its optimal application rates, and hydrogel synthesis have been extensively studied, notably by Professor A.T. Djalilov. In addition, Professors M.Kh. Khamidov, A.T. Salokhiddinov, N.B. Egamberdiyev, and other scholars have investigated the role of hydrogels in improving water use efficiency in cotton and companion crop cultivation.

In the current global context, where climate change and ecological challenges are intensifying—particularly in Central Asian countries like Uzbekistan—water scarcity is becoming more acute. According to data from the AgroUz website, while droughts occurred once every 6–8 years before 2000, in recent decades, such events are now repeating every 2–3 years [2].

These negative trends naturally pose substantial challenges for the development of agriculture. Inadequate water supply for crops leads to reduced yields and deterioration in crop quality.

Therefore, the widespread implementation of water-saving technologies in agricultural production and the use of modern agro-technologies that enhance land and water resource efficiency have become critical and urgent needs of our time.

Among such technologies, the use of polymer hydrogels in irrigated lands stands out as an effective method.

Noteworthy are the scientific investigations of M.Kh. Khamidov, A.T. Salokhiddinov, N.B. Egamberdiyev, and others, who studied the impact of hydrogels on water savings when growing cotton and other associated crops. Their findings revealed that in both hydromorphic and automorphic soils, applying hydrogel allowed a 1,25–1,3 times reduction in irrigation water consumption, a decrease of one irrigation event, and up to 10% increase in yield. Hydrogel is a super-absorbent polymer capable of absorbing large amounts of water and gradually releasing it into the surrounding soil environment when needed. It helps retain moisture in the soil over extended periods. Experts note that 10 grams of hydrogel can retain 2.5 to 4 liters of water, and when used correctly, it can save 20–40% of irrigation water.

Considering these facts and the adverse effects of current trends, we undertook research under hydromorphic and meadow sierozem soils with medium to heavy loam texture, aiming to preserve soil productivity, improve meliorative conditions, and enhance the efficient use of water resources. At the same time, our goal was to support the economic sustainability of farming households through the application of hydrogel-based water-saving technologies.

Results: In our field experiments, a locally produced polymer hydrogel was applied at a rate of 40 kg per hectare during the joint cultivation of cotton and soybean. The study aimed to assess the effects of hydrogel and intercropping on the agro-physical, water-physical, and agrochemical properties of the soil, as well as on irrigation regimes, seasonal water norms, and the number of irrigation events.

The field trials were conducted using three experimental variants: Variant 1 (Control): Conventional cotton cultivation under production conditions without hydrogel. Variant 2 (Intercropping with Hydrogel): Cotton and soybean were cultivated together, with polymer hydrogel applied at a depth of 15–18 cm before sowing. Variant 3 (Cotton with Hydrogel): Similar to Variant 2, but only cotton was grown with the application of hydrogel. In Variants 1 and 3 cotton plant density ranged from 119 000 to 123 000 plants per hectare. In Variant 2, the total plant density was higher—122 000 to 128 000 plants per hectare, consisting of 51 000–53 000 soybean plants and 71 000–75 000 cotton plants. As of September 1, boll development data were as follows: In the control variant (Variant 1), the average number of bolls per plant was 11,8 with 5,5 open bolls. In the cotton+soybean intercropping variant (Variant 2), the figures were 13,2 and 5,4, respectively. In Variant 3, the numbers were 12,3 and 5,3, respectively—0,9 and 0.1 less than in the intercropped variant. By the same date, the main stem height of the soybean plants reached 108.6 cm, and the average number of pods per plant was 104,7.

Figure 1. Graph of Cotton Growth and Yield According to Cultivation Methods

Calculations of cotton yield showed that in the control variant, the average cotton yield amounted to 28,6 centners per hectare, while in the variant where cotton and soybean were cultivated together, it was 20,9 centners per hectare. In the third variant, where cotton was grown with the application of polymer hydrogel, the highest cotton yield of 30,1 centners per hectare was achieved.

However, the most remarkable aspect is that although cotton yield was significantly lower in the intercropping variant compared to the mono-cropped cotton variant, an additional yield of 18,2 centners per hectare of soybean grain was obtained.

Observations on irrigation practices in the experimental field showed that 840 to 1260 m³/ha of water was used for each irrigation event, and a total of 5660 to 4695 m³/ha was applied throughout the season. The number of irrigations was five, with the first irrigation lasting 18 hours.

In the following irrigations, the duration in the control variant ranged from 18 to 20 hours, while in the hydrogel-treated variant, the irrigation duration was reduced to 14–17 hours.

Table 1. Number of Irrigations and Seasonal Water Norms in the Experimental Field

Variant	Number of Irrigations (times)	Water Use per Irrigation (m ³ /ha)	Total Seasonal Water Use (m ³ /ha)	Duration of First Irrigation (hours)	Duration of Subsequent Irrigations (hours)
Cotton (Control)	5	840 – 1260	5660	18	18 – 20
Cotton + Soybean (with hydrogel)	5	840 – 1260	4695	18	14 – 17
Cotton (with hydrogel only)	5	840 – 1260	4695	18	14 – 17

Table 2. Number of Irrigations and Seasonal Water Norms in the Experimental Field

Variant	1st Irrigation (m ³ /ha)	2nd Irrigation (m ³ /ha)	3rd Irrigation (m ³ /ha)	4th Irrigation (m ³ /ha)	5th Irrigation (m ³ /ha)	Seasonal Water Use (m ³ /ha)
Conventional method (control)	840	1180	1210	1260	1170	5660
With hydrogel (Variants 2 and 3)	840	930	975	1030	920	4695

This can be attributed to the fact that soil moisture content in the hydrogel-treated variant was 8–11% higher compared to the control. It is worth noting that, currently, water use in farming operations is organized based on a fixed irrigation schedule. Therefore, in both variants, irrigation events were conducted simultaneously. The only difference between the treatments was that irrigation rates and durations were adjusted based on soil moisture content, as presented in Table 2.

Figure 1. Experimental field: cotton + soybean (left) and cotton with hydrogel treatments
Figure 2. Phenological observation process in the experimental field

Recommendations: It is recommended to apply 40 kg/ha of polymer hydrogel, produced from local raw materials, under the hydromorphic, medium and heavy loamy sierozem soils of the Tashkent region in order to improve irrigation water use efficiency. When cotton is cultivated using this method, it is possible to achieve a 1.5 c/ha higher yield compared to the control, while also reducing irrigation water use by 15–17%.

Conclusions: Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that in order to increase the efficiency of irrigation water use in the cultivation of cotton and associated crops, the application of 40 kg/ha of polymer hydrogel made from local raw materials is recommended. This approach allows for a 15–18% reduction in seasonal water consumption. Moreover, when cotton is cultivated with hydrogel, it is possible to obtain a 1.5 c/ha higher yield compared to the control variant

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